

Historical Consideration On Vocal Composition Of Thailand

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Abstract

Through the ages, traditional composition education in Thailand has been seen as non-academic in its development and progression. This has affected people's perceptions. The continuation of their way of life was made possible by this method for them. The Buddhist monasteries, on the other hand, served as a support structure for traditional composition teaching in Thailand, and formal, systematic ensembles may be found in the palaces of families and the houses of nobility. Not only were these places where compositional art flourished as a result of the presence of highly skilled composers, but they were also places where the family and officers enthusiastically sponsored and participated, with some of the composers and composers being well-known Thailand traditional composers and composers, among others. There has been a substantial contribution to the discipline via their performances and compositions." From the time of the Siamese coup d'état in 1932 until the current day, social and political upheaval have had a significant impact on the standing of traditional Thai composition.

In its commercial existence, the vocal composition is often described as having its beginnings in the Western hemisphere, and it has been the subject of intense controversy in Anglophone academic circles for many years. Political economics is one of the most successful approaches to take, with the traditional sector being considered largely as an example of capitalism with the objective of maximization profit as its primary focus. A considerable decline in the tendency toward monopolization of numerous traditional areas as a consequence of these particular tendencies has been seen across the board as a result of these specific tendencies.

Introduction

As a result, it will be claimed that the vocal composition industry in Thailand represents a kind of variation on Adorno's idea of mass vocal composition, echoing essential aspects of his description but yet diverging in fundamental ways from it. Although certain academics, both Thai and non-Thai, have investigated Thailand's vocal composition with a special emphasis on Thailand's composition and composition in general as their primary focus. In addition, while the term "Thailand vocal composition" has been widely used by these composers, it has been used more often than not as a term for all compositional styles currently in circulation with the notable exceptions being traditional Thailand classical composition

Because it has been stated that mainstream pop composition is the only generation that should legitimately be named Thailand vocal composition, the term will be used in a much more limited sense for this article, to refer only to mainstream pop composition.

The absence of academic study on the mainstream pop composition business in Thailand until now has resulted in the particular structure and dynamics of the Thailand sector having little impact on disputes among mostly Western composers who are involved in the vocal composition industry. However, the contributions that this study has the potential to make are substantial in scope. Given the fact that Thailand vocal composition is a subject that is seldom studied in both Thai and non-Thai academic institutions, there are certain to be some difficulties faced throughout a study in this area. Thailand's vocal composition and the great compositions are published in the Thai language; this study will focus on the issue of vocal composition in Thailand. Secondly, there are no official records of Thailand vocal composition that might be used as official points of reference in the absence of official records. This has necessitated the collection of information from a variety of sources, including newspapers, composition publications, and personal interviews, among others.

Theoretical Framework

According to Aristotle, what can be learned via the discipline of *theoria* (theory) is not the same as what can be achieved through the discipline of *poiesis* (creation) or *praxis* (practice) (practice). While *theoria* is concerned with the quest of truth in an absolute sense, *poiesis* is concerned with the creation of a product, and

praxis is concerned with the discipline by which action is applied to a current task. Put another way, these concepts are associated with three different types of domains: knowing; creating; and doing; and doing. The classes in Aristotle's taxonomy, on the other hand, were not disconnected or diametrically opposed things, but were rather interconnected and interdependent. As Paulo Freire (1921–1997) put it, "We discover two dimensions, contemplation and action, in such radical interplay that when one is sacrificed—even to a little degree—the other suffers as soon as the first." Freire was a Brazilian educationalist who lived from 1921 to 1997.

It may seem that the oldest division of compositional knowledge separated composition theory from composition; however Aristides classed composition as practical compositional knowledge, which may imply that the earliest division of compositional knowledge separated composition theory from composition. However, Aristotle's division of knowledge affects Aristides' description of composition as practical—alongside performance—rather than theoretical, which is in line with Aristotle's division of knowledge. The search of truth, or *theoria*, is largely concerned with ontological problems, such as: What is the nature of composition? Music theory, in the opinion of Aristides, has nothing to do with descriptive or analytical examinations of pieces of composition, or with the invention or right performance of such pieces of composition. It was instead the pursuit of information about what has subsequently become the scientific study of acoustics as well as many disciplines of mathematics that was known as *compositiona theoretica*, or harmonics, as the field was frequently referred to.

It has been said that composition is the most universal of all the arts in terms of its appeal and acceptability, and that this is true. Regardless of country, composition acts as a common language that is used to communicate innermost thoughts and aspirations, promote awareness of various issues, explain, portray – and criticize – socio-political landscapes, and generate funds for charitable organizations. Throughout history, composition has shown to be quite useful, and it has followed humanity on his many pursuits. Music is also all-encompassing in the sense that it may be appreciated and even loved regardless of the composer or the context in which the piece was produced — this is evidence that composition, like all other arts, is transcendental in its reach and meaning. This means that it may be enjoyed with or without the presence of its creator, allowing composition to be appreciated on a subjective level beyond any academic criteria. But, of course, this idea must be handled with care in order to avoid any misunderstandings from arising.

However, although composition is universal, it is also endowed with individuality – that is, with originality – which varies from one country, one generation, and one milieu to another. This is because composition is a product of its time and place. Consequently, as Hila (2004) points out, composition may be defined as "a collective manifestation of the compositional genius of a specific people," in the sense of representing the people's collective identity as well as their mindset and struggle. A country may be defined by its composition, and a nation can define its own composition as a result.

For the same reason that so much other traditional composition in South East Asia does, Thailand composition relies heavily on oral tradition, which is handed down from instructors to students. Rather than inviting artists to share their detailed expertise or finding a way to make it available, there has been no effort made to encourage them to do so.

A further issue is that traditionally in Thailand vocal composition, the pursuit of composition as a career, whether as a performer or as a researcher working in the subject of composition, was not seen as a legitimate source of serious employment. Consequently, there have been no academic institutions in Thailand where study on Thailand composition has been possible as a result of these beliefs.

A social structure has developed as a result of the advent of new mores and concepts. This structure is driven by a deep reverence for City society and civilization in the vast majority of circumstances. As with its counterpart composition in the fields of food, clothing, and machinery, imported composition has emerged as an essential luxury, providing not only a source of entertainment and leisure but also a source of social prestige.

There has been a pushback against the conditioning of notions that have been spread for millennia by tradition icons of modern civilization among the more educated and intelligent parts of society. This answer expressed itself in the form of patriotic sentiments throughout the majority of the eighteenth century and beyond, which became more widespread in all sectors of social and political life over the course of World's historical development.

There are two schools of thought: one is self-confidence in one's ability to compete with the dominant vocal composition for equality in all spheres of intellectual, physical, and material pursuits, and another is a strong sense of one's own identity as a people, the achievement of which could serve as the ultimate measure of liberation from the shackles of historicism and tradition subjugation. Despite the fact that the two schools of thought seem to be incompatible, they are not.

DISCUSSION

The development of modern Thailand composition's current character, in particular, can be traced back to their people historical and tradition battles, as well as a larger sense of nationalist identity. The purpose of this study is to examine the origins, development, current tendencies, and ramifications of this specific element of

Thailand vocal composition as an acculturated response to westernization, and to use it as a starting point for a broader discussion of the phenomenon of tradition change in the Thailand.

Out of all of the styles mentioned above, the voice production employed for phleegpynblUia is the most close to that of the composition tradition, despite the fact that distinct regional folk styles use a variety of diverse approaches. The projection of the voice in these folk forms is done in a "kept back" fashion. Suntharawaathin advises composition song performers to feel the vibration in their chests while singing in order to produce a more controlled sound, according to the expert which means that the voice is projected more. Apart from this, the primary characteristic of Thailand composition singing that separates it from the other generations is the stiffness of the throat and the abundance of nasality in the performance.

"How can they sing with such a voice?" or anything along those lines is often asked of me by those who have listened to Thailand composition singing. The explanation is that the voice must be seen as a kind of compositional instrument in order to be understood. Learning how to generate this tone of voice does not seem to have been a challenge for previous generations of learners. The difficulty, according to him, has existed since the 1970s, and she claims she has never had a problem with teaching a pupil to sing.

Due to the fact that Thailand song melodies have only ever existed in oral form, researching their history is more difficult. Although some old lyrics have been written down, the melodies have only ever been passed down through the generations by oral transmission from teacher to pupil and from old singers to young.

The 'classic' or Bangkok period [which] can be considered as a culmination of compositional evolution that probably began... in the fourteenth and fifteenth centuries with the rise of Ayuthaya [Ayutthaya] as the capital] is described by Morton as "what we know today of Thailand composition is in actuality only of the nineteenth and twentieth centuries" Due to its might and the presence of several tough and successful warriors, the Empire of Ayutthaya maintained a high degree of unity for about two hundred years (15th- 17th century), creating a healthy environment in which civilizations could develop.

Even farther back in antiquity, before the Ayutthaya era, a significant number of peoples with distinct identities were dispersed over the Indochinese peninsula, and it is possible to trace the history of the people of present-day Thailand back to this time period. Thailand people, according to historians, are a group of people who share a shared language and tradition identity known as Tai.

Wyatt expresses himself "It was just a thousand years ago that the individuals who introduced the essential characteristics of current Thailand identity to what is now Thailand arrived in the central region of the Indochinese peninsula. Only after many centuries of contact between Tai and indigenous and immigrant vocal compositions has a 'Thailand' vocal composition, a civilisation, and an identity evolved as the outcome of this interaction. The indigenous civilizations were the Mon and the Khmer, while the immigrants were mostly Chinese and Indian in origin. However, no research has precisely shown how the composition of these civilizations came to be, nor has any study produced definite proof of what the sound of their composition was like before then. Despite the fact that only a few pieces of evidence from archaeological sites such as the ancient temple of Angkor Wat and other similar finds show images of compositional instruments being played, the melodies that were played and, in particular, the songs that were sung, remain shrouded in ancient darkness.

The time immediately preceding the Ayutthaya is known as the SukhoThailand and it is this period that most contemporary Thailand consider to be the "true" beginning of their country's history. It is also the time period in which the Thailand people were the most dominant race on the continent of Southeast Asia at the time.

The study of composition during that era is entirely dependent on stone inscriptions which were carved during the reign of King Ramkhamhaeng and are now in the possession of the Thailand National Museum (1279-98). In addition to snaglfian and Sling Kbitb*, there are certain terms on them that are related to singing: The word snag may be translated as "sound" in certain contexts. snag Jyyaa, according to Montrii Traamdod (1984), refers to a sound that is composed of melody and rhythm, while snag Kababas, according to Traamdod (1984), refers to free melodic vocalisation. Using this interpretation of these two meanings, Although the term Jfynn is no longer in use, the term kbnba appears in many works of literature from the later Ayutthaya period.

Siam conquered Angkor in 1352 and remained in control of the city until 1357. Thousands of Khmer citizens, including artists and high-ranking government officials, were deported to Thailand in large groups. Ninety thousand Cambodians were taken to the Thailand capital of Ayutthaya in a year, in 1393.

When Thailand annexed and exploited Khmer vocal composition during the subsequent wars, it did so with a clear understanding of its importance: "When the Siamese (Thailand) conquered and destroyed the Khmers, they were themselves conquered by the beauty of the Khmer arts... and protected, loved, and nurtured" the vocal composition. It is quite probable that Khmer composition had an effect on Thailand composition during the period. A good example of this blending of vocal compositions can be seen in highly regarded contemporary Thailand songs such both of which are based on names that exist in an old Khmer folk story. He is a prince from a place beyond the sea (believed to be India), and N&ag is a native Khmer lady from the land beyond the sea.

Through Buddhism, the Indians had a direct impact on the Thailand people as well. The Pali language, which was used in Buddhist chants, was also used in literary works such as Mahaachdad Kham Luuarj ("The

great incarnation [of the Buddha]: composition version") and other such "high" literary works of the composition, such as Mahaachdad Kham Luuarj ("The great incarnation [of the Buddha]: composition version"). During the reign of King Narai, a literary style known as chan, which can be found in Pali script, progressively supplanted other forms of composition literature in the development of composition literature and became immensely popular (1656-88). It was also composed in the Kham Chan, a narrative of the Buddha and one of the most renowned works of Thailand classical literature, which is utilized for shadow-puppet theatre. While the cAizform was utilized by the composition for their literature, the Jfe/zform, which is an indigenous form of mainland Southeast Asia, was used by the general public.

In addition, there is a long heritage of Hindu recited scriptures in Thailand, which is known as oogkma and is performed by a Brahmin, which is also known as oogkma. The oogkaon chlgmiaz, often known as the "text for cursing water," is a very significant passage. When the army swears an oath of allegiance to the monarch, their pledge is reaffirmed by the placement of their weapons in a big cauldron filled with water, which is conducted once a year. As a result of the curse placed on the water, the Brahmin claims that anyone who betrays their king and country will be slaughtered by the weapons concealed inside it, amongst other things.

The original form of the composition vocal tradition can perhaps be discerned in contemporary folk songs and even songs known as mo3kimvih.ich are said to be the property of the people who live in the northeastern part of Thailand known as khonlm w; or "Laotians," and who are said to be descended from the family. Court and commoner composition were constantly influencing one another: they shared compositional instruments, repertoires, and vocal technical phrases such as "chant" and "aria" "fa in the word"

Thailand's songs were not originally kept in recorded form until the 17th century, with both lyrics and melodies being transcribed, and even then, it was done so only by foreigners.

Gervaise's 1688 description of Siam contains a transcription of the song "Sout Chai" on two five-line staves in duple meter, with a romanized Thailand text beneath, on two five-line staves in duple meter. As an additional feature of the report to King Louis XIV of France there is a song transcribed in Western staff notation that is unrelated to any surviving piece and is currently known to Thailand composers as Samoon is the name of a piece composed by Simon de la Loub6re and published in Loub6re. Because both of the songs transcribed include just a little amount of ppan, they are now categorized as "full text" songs, despite the fact that they noted that pyun. It was used in one of the songs. The same can be said about these two songs, which served only for amusement reasons and were only played once.

The application of the Aristotelian division of knowledge to composition by Aristides had a long-lasting influence on the trajectory of composition instruction, which continued far into the nineteenth century. In his writings on composition, Aristides addressed themes of both *theoria* and *praxis* within any specific composition, which is a common theme among those who have written about composition. All topics pertaining to vocal or instrumental composition, on the other hand, were recognized from the beginning as the pursuit of *praxis*, or the 'doing' of composition. Much of what has subsequently been categorized as composition theory was included in writings on *praxis*, such as the analysis or study of specific compositional pieces, among other things. In this sense, there was originally no distinction between what has now been established as the distinct areas of composition theory and composition.

Since most compositional transmission occurred orally before the ninth century and most compositional generation occurred extemporaneously until the fifteenth, education of composition can only be determined via written treatises, as opposed to the tiny corpus of notated composition. But many of the treatises on compositional knowledge that have been written from antiquity and have survived until the middle Ages have merely catalogued compositional information and are not clearly descriptive or prescriptive in nature. The few remaining texts make it impossible to determine whether the theory or the practice emerged first: the theory or the practice. A number of different techniques emerged, each with varied degrees of influence from either an existing body of compositional units or a set of constraining compositional parameters.

In this way, this technique was beneficial in the development of an increasingly delicate sensitivity toward the discovery of compositional difficulties as it progressed through the stages. Students get the capacity to articulate a notion via compositional methods as a result of the discovery and solution of such 'issues.' At about the same time as the movement in pedagogical practice from individual study to class teaching started, the study of Harmony found itself at the core of curriculum at composition institutions. When combined with a concentrated study of harmony and compositional analysis, the continued use of practical methods such as counterpoint and thoroughbass would eventually result in a division between composition theory and composition as two distinct fields of study in the conservatory during the nineteenth century.

Following their human experience and practice, they believe that chanting summons the spirits, who then express thanks and appreciation while also providing protection and blessings to those who participate. Melisma, call and response, and free rhythm are all types of vocal expression that are differentiated by the presence of a deep vocal vibration expression in their delivery. In contrast to Western music, traditional indigenous music does not establish a clear identity in the same way that Western music does; rather, it

symbolizes the identity of the Upland people via the usage of the tone system that they have developed for themselves (the use of pentatonic scale).

Themes such as self-expression, nationality, and embodiment are some of the topics she explores in her musical composition. The rapid development of new media has played a role in the acceleration of globalization that has taken place in recent decades. Human civilization and relationships have been linked and complicated by new media, yet the very existence of intercultural communication as a fundamental method of communication is being threatened by new media. Achieving viability as an identity construct and as a theoretical object of research is secured since the hybridity shown in this difference was so vital to her performative identity. Following the conclusions of this study, the features of globalization that are dynamic, ubiquitous, hybridized and interrelated as well as individually potent have been accentuated via the use of new media. Considering that the distance between different geographical locations has been decreased, as well as the compressed nature of time in this era of technology communication, many people believe that local, national, and global space are out of date in this age of technology communication.

Expanding interest in the act of composition as a cognitive activity, particularly around the start of the twentieth century, is a reflection of the growing interest in psychology at that time as well. A precise concept of creativity, on the other hand, was not forthcoming. Carl Jung (1875–1961), the father of analytical psychology, defined the popular concept of the creative process as "the development of something new [that] is not done by the brain, but by the play impulse working out of inner need," which is a hazy description of the creative process.

Thailand traditional singing is a one-of-a-kind art form because of its ornately complicated procedures, which requires a keen sense of recall and years of intensive training. Several strategies are used by a vocalist in order to convey melodic lyrics and melismata to an audience. Instructional practices may be passed on from one person to another. A decrease in the number of Thailand traditional singing pupils, along with an aging population of famous vocal teachers, has resulted in a decrease in the number of talented learners.

For the same reason that so much other traditional composition in South East Asia does, Thailand composition relies heavily on oral tradition, which is handed down from instructors to students. Rather than inviting artists to share their detailed expertise or finding a way to make it available, there has been no effort made to encourage them to do so.

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When Western-style singing started to infiltrate Thailand society, it brought with it many other types of voice production that could not be integrated or absorbed because they were so different from the traditional technique of producing voice. Because other styles, such as the phleegphebstyiv, have such a great effect on society, it is difficult for a singing instructor today to teach Thailand voice production to a pupil. I, too, have had similar difficulties when teaching Thailand students, as well as non-Thailand, in the United Kingdom and the Netherlands. Thailand voice is a foreign form of singing to most individuals in the contemporary world, and the younger the learner is when they begin instruction, the more easily they will adapt to the style.

Thailand composition singing involves extensive use of the throat in the creation of the sound; this is referred to as Mugkhoo in Thailand, which literally translates as "neckball" (neckball). According to Prasadthikun, the proper technique to sing Thailand composition songs is to sing in the style of the phrase "luugkhoo" was not used by Suntharawaathin, although he did discuss the employment of "neck muscles" in both singing and in the production of certain technical effects. It is used to describe to certain vocal techniques that demand "flexibility" of the throat in order to be produced: methods such as khm n (a kind of vibrato).

The applications seem to be the most often mentioned aspects throughout performance and tuition. Another element that has been disputed is the degree to which the mouth should be opened when singing, with various vocalists having differing ideas on this. Generally speaking, though, a virtually closed-mouth approach with almost hard lips is preferred, especially while singing or performing.

It seems that the majority of vocalists will sing at the highest range they are capable of. It is only utilized when the melody is higher than the top of their range, requiring them to lower their pitch and therefore slip down the scale. When the melody permits it, they will go back to the upper register once again. Thailand composition singing, according to some vocalists, is characterized by the use of a high register while singing. Many vocalists have said that this is due to the fact that there were no microphones or amplifiers accessible in the past, and as a result, the singers were forced to sing loudly and in a high range in order to be heard - especially when the ensemble joined in. This hypothesis seems to be valid since current vocalists, who would typically sing in a high range, would transition to a lower scale when a microphone is employed, such as in a recording studio, proving that the idea is correct. When singers who were recorded in the early 1900s/20 are listened to, the majority of them sing in a very high register; this may be due to the fact that they were not using the microphone in the same way that modern singers do, or it may simply be due to the fact that they lacked proper microphone technique at the time. Some singers criticize the excessive use of a high register, claiming that such singing only "tells the narrative" and fails to communicate the actual emotion of the lyrics because the vocal chords have been strained to the point where they are unable to soften the voice. They like to speak in the medium range of their voice, and only on rare occasions do they utilize the upper range of their voice.

CONCLUSION

As a result of this, Thailand singers make extensive use of the falsetto voice, which allows them to sing at the upper end of the scale rather than merely at the top of their specific range. The falsetto voice must be used with caution: the "absolute" falsetto produces an unpleasant sound known in Thailand as sitagphiiot, which translates as "ghost voice." When it comes to sound, half-and-half between the falsetto and the full voice is desirable. Singers must negotiate their way through a piece in order to achieve a balance between the two types of sound; this negotiation approach is referred to as diin suagov.

Note that the sound of Thailand singing is quite similar to the sound of two traditional Thailand instruments: the piinajsobo) and the seesaam, and that one of these two instruments may be used to accompany and/or replicate vocal melodies during a performance may be used in place of the p iiand suusaam saajqsq if the p iiand suusaam saajqsq are not readily accessible.) It has been used to accompany singing in ensembles from the Ayutthaya era (14th to 18th centuries), at some point in the history of the instrument. The timbre of the instrument may have had an impact on the singing voice to some degree since it was performed concurrently with the vocal portion and assisted the singers with the vocal melody. Because the ptinajcan. can accurately reproduce the timbre of singing or even human speech, it is utilized to impersonate the voice in wmi doo1, chuj chaaj1 and stiuadkhiyhddpit, among other works. Ptim J players (and, in certain cases, the sou saam iw/jf players in mahoodiensembles) must pay special attention to the vocal line and copy it as precisely as possible in order to perform the wibi dbog and chujchaajmelodies correctly. A new book, Khorjlaajthoor) (1995), delves into the world of performance methods for the piinaj'm and the imitation of chuj chaajm siodies, offering complete descriptions of particular procedures that are utilized to copy certain vowels and consonants. The p tin a j is also used to represent the voice itself in certain cases. The four phi players, for example, use their

instruments to simulate a conversation in the piece. They make remarks, respond with jokes, and otherwise behave as if they were speaking. Sanbdurijaarj (1866-1949), preferred to utilize the instrument to deliver directions to his subordinates rather than speaking to them in front of others.

In terms of the human voice itself, there is no systematic classification system in place. The songs are always performed in unison, even when they are in a chorus; there are no separate parts for various voices even in a chorus. The division is simply established into males and females, with no mention of the sort of voice used, however persons are sometimes noted for having an especially high register in their voice. A few philosophers have sought to categorize the Thailand voice into groups based on the Western system: s/lag suugor high voice, sitagklaagot medium voice, and mag dim, low voice; nevertheless, such concepts of categorizing the voice based on its range are not widely accepted by singers. Singers, on the other hand, constantly remark on the quality of their voices, using the word siag m eaning "fine voice" to denote an excellent voice.

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Even farther back in antiquity, before the Ayutthaya era, a significant number of peoples with distinct identities were dispersed over the Indochinese peninsula, and it is possible to trace the history of the people of present-day Thailand back to this time period. Thailand people, according to historians, are a group of people who share a shared language and tradition identity known as Tai.

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